

Completion of the Provision in Civil Procedure Law

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Abstract

In our law, there are institutions of correction for the correction of material errors and the explanation of unclear or contradictory statements after the court gives a verdict and withdraws from the file. With the HMK article 305/A, the institution of completing the provision has been added to eliminate the deficiencies in the provision. In fact, the institution of the completion of the judgment is not foreign to our law, and with the completion of the judgment against the judgment rendered by the arbitrators in the arbitration proceedings, complementary decisions may be requested in the matters that have not been decided despite the fact that it was brought forward during the proceedings (HMK article.437). Therefore, in

Turkish law, the institution of completion of the judgment has been in existence since 1 October 2011, when HMK No. 6100 came into force. With the addition of Article 305/A to the HMK with Article 27 of the Law. It is essential that the trials are conducted in a healthy manner by the courts and that all the claims put forward by the parties within the scope of the case are fully and completely adjudicated . However, there are cases where the courts make incomplete decisions regarding the claims of the parties due to reasons such as carelessness, forgetfulness, negligence and overlooked due to the workload. To eliminate such deficiencies and to include the need to be passed on judicially in the final decision, the legislator has added the "completion of the judgment" way to the HMK with Article 27 of the Law No. 7251 on the Amendment of Civil Procedures and Some Laws. Law of Civil Procedure art. Completion of the provision in 305/A is foreseen in its regulation.

Keywords: *Completion of Judgment in Civil Procedure Law, Civil Procedure Law, Completion of Judgment, Judgment in Civil Procedure Law, Completion of Judgment in Civil Procedure*

1. Introduction

We can define the completion of the provision as the making of an additional decision on matters that were not partially or completely decided, although it was brought forward by the parties during the trial process and the subject of a lawsuit should be taken into consideration by the court ex officio.

According to the opinion in the doctrine, the regulation to complete the provision was accepted to fill this deficiency after the court did not decide on one or more of the results of the claimant's demand ¹.

2. Legal nature

There is no clear regulation in the law regarding the legal nature of the institution of completion of the provision. However, the legal nature of the institution in question is narrow and technically not a legal remedy. Because the completion of the provision has neither the transferring nor the suspensive effect, which are the typical characteristics of legal remedies in

1 M. Özkes, O. Atalay and H. Pekanttez (2020). Evaluation of Law No. 7251 Amending the Code of Civil Procedure. Journal of the Union of Turkish Bar Associations. Ankara: Union of Turkish Bar Associations, Issue: 150, p. 280.

a narrow and technical sense ². As it can be understood from the text of the article, the completion of the provision does not have a transponder attachment. Because the completion of the judgment is requested not from the higher court, but from the court that made the original decision. In addition, it does not have the effect of delaying the completion of the provision. That is, the finalization of the judgment cannot be prevented by applying this way, but against a finalized decision, it can be requested to complete the judgment if the application period has not expired.

As a result, it can be said that the completion of the judgment is a legal remedy since it provides the opportunity to apply against a final decision. In the doctrine, the legal remedy is expressed as the technical equivalent of the inspection and review of the legal remedies ³. In a broad sense, legal remedy is defined as any procedural tool used for the purpose of protecting or exercising a right in procedural law. Again, according to the same opinion, it is stated which types of legal applications should be accepted as legal remedies. According to this view, the remedies foreseen for the re-evaluation of the decision rendered by the same court should be accepted as a legal remedy since it is a re-examination of the decision rather than a real inspection ⁴.

Namely, an important consequence of its acceptance as a legal remedy is seen in terms of constitutional complaint. Since in our law, the remedies must be exhausted before making an individual application to the Constitutional Court, the applicants are required to resort to this remedy after exhausting the way to complete the verdict. The German Constitutional Court also decided that the provision should be exhausted if the conditions exist, before resorting to this remedy on the grounds that ⁵the constitutional complaint is of secondary nature and that legal remedies should be exhausted .

3. Aim

Completion of the provision becomes effective in terms of matters that were claimed by the parties in the trial but were not partially or fully decided by the court, although no will has

²Pekcanitez/Atalay/Özokes, Usul, p 436.

³Özokes, Pekcanitez Usul, p.2155.

⁴Özokes, Pekcanitez Usul, p.2156.

⁵BVerfG, 274.2000, 1 BVR 2007/99.

been expressed in the judgment, either positively or negatively, that is, the forgotten requests or although it is required to be passed on judicially on their own accord ⁶. If the demands of the parties are not reflected in the judgment and the courts do not decide on matters such as litigation expenses and in this context, especially attorney's fees, which should be decided by themselves, the said deficiencies can be eliminated by the institution of the completion of the judgment. In other words, the purpose of completing the provision is not to re-examine the provision, but to correct the deficiencies in the provision ⁷. According to Pekcanitez, the completion of the provision also aims to provide effective legal protection in this context.

According to the dominant view in German law, the purpose of completing the Judgment is to complete the deficiency in matters of dispute or claims that have not been decided although it is necessary to be decided by the court; It is to allow ⁸the courts to inspect themselves . The point to be considered here is that the issue requested by the parties or to be considered ex officio by the court should be forgotten, in other words, it should be overlooked/overlooked. However, if the court does not decide on the above-mentioned issues, it should be resolved not by the completion of the judgment, but by an appeal against the decision. It is also possible to open a new lawsuit regarding the request that has not been decided despite the request.

4. Conditions

As we will explain in detail below, several conditions must be met at the same time for the judgment to be complete. In other words, in order for the parties to make a request for completion, the existence of a final decision given by the court, the claims of the parties in the final decision in question or a matter that should be decided ex officio by the court should not have been decided, and a request for completion should be submitted to the court that made the decision within 30 days. .

6Boran Güneysu, Decision in Civil Procedure Law, P.275.Ankara-2014; M. Özkes, O. Atalay and H. Pekcantez (2020). Evaluation of Law No. 7251 Amending the Code of Civil Procedure. Journal of the Union of Turkish Bar Associations. Ankara: Union of Turkish Bar Associations, Issue: 150, p. 280.

7Belgin Güneş, p.315.

8Akkaya, Completion of the judgment in Civil Procedure Law, Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli University Faculty of Law Journal C. XXV, No.1 p.25. footnote.11.

4.1. Finding the final decision

As it is known, as a rule, after the court makes the final decision on the dispute, the court is dismissed from that file, that is, it withdraws its hand from the file. In addition, since the court does not give an ex officio authority to correct the neglected or forgotten matters with Article 305/A of the HMK, it makes a final decision with the request, and the file that it has seized is brought before it to make an additional decision. In other words, the institution of completion of the judgment is one of the exceptions to the judge's withdrawal from the file.

In the completion of the provision, the legislator used the concept of final decision, which did not say "judgment", unlike the correction and clarification of the provision. Even further, the distinction between procedural and substantive final decisions is not made.

HMK ARTICLE 305/A- (1) Each of the parties may request an additional decision within one month following the notification of the final decision, in matters that have not been fully or partially decided, although it is required to be brought forward in the trial or to be passed on judicially on its own. Legal action can be taken against this decision.

As it can be understood from the text of the article, the legislator used the term "final decision". What should be understood from the concept of final decision in civil procedural law are substantive and procedural decisions. (m.294.1). Therefore, with the final decisions regarding the merits and procedures, an application may be made to the institution of the completion of the opposite judgment.

4.1.1. Uncontested judicial decisions

Final decisions on uncontested judicial decisions may also be requested to complete the judgment. That is, although uncontested judicial decisions do not constitute a final judgment in material terms (art. 388), in cases where there is no regulation regarding the contested judicial rules, general provisions will be applied, so it can be requested to complete the judgment against uncontested judicial decisions⁹. However, it should be noted that in the doctrine, it is stated that uncontested judicial decisions do not constitute a final judgment in material terms, that is,

⁹Akkaya, pages36.

the way to complete the judgment should not be applied, since the same court may be requested to change the decision against the decision.

4.1.2. Temporary legal protection decisions

As explained above, the existence of a final decision is essential for the completion of the judgment. In that case, it cannot be demanded to complete the provision in temporary legal protection measures and decisions. Because it is understood from article 341.1 that temporary legal protection decisions are not accepted as final decisions in our law. In the relevant article, temporary legal protection and final decisions are specified separately.

4.1.3. Interim decisions

Article 305/A of the HMK does not apply to interim decisions either. Although there is no clear regulation in our law regarding the completion of the interim decision, the court can make the completion of the interim decision ex officio and upon request. That is, unless the defect in the interim decision creates a procedural right in favor of the parties, it can be returned or changed by the court ex officio or upon request¹⁰. It is possible to reach the same conclusion against the interim decisions that may be requested to be fulfilled through forced execution. In summary, considering that the most important condition sought for the completion of the judgment is the final decision, it is not possible to apply HMK 305/A since it is not a final decision even if there is an interim decision with enforcement capability.

4.1.4. District Court decisions

Since the decisions made by the BAM are also final decisions, it may well be demanded to complete the judgment against these decisions. The point that needs to be discussed here is that the Regional Court of Justice has the authority to examine both as a first instance and a higher degree in accordance with the HMK. If the court of first instance examines the file on the merits, it can undoubtedly be demanded to complete the judgment against the decision, since the first-instance trial procedure will undoubtedly be applied. At the same time, if it evaluates as a court

¹⁰Akkaya, pages35; Boran Güneysu, p.161.

of appeal, it may be requested that the judgment be finalized, since the decision is final, although there is no clarity in the law regarding this issue.

4.1.5. Supreme Court decisions

There is no clarity as to which court decisions can be claimed against in the finalization of the judgment, as in the correction and correction of the judgment. However, as it is accepted in the doctrine and practice, it can be applied against the decisions of the Court of Cassation to complete the judgment, as in the correction and correction of the judgment.

4.2.Lack of/gap in the provision

In general, in Article 305/A of the HMK, the completion of the judgment can be requested "*in matters that have not been fully or partially decided, although it is required to be brought forward in the trial or to be adjudicated on its own*". As it can be understood in the text of the article, the issues that are not fully or partially decided are divided into two as "*put forward in the trial*" and "*subject to a verdict*".

4.2.1. Claim made at trial

In the final decision, the reasons for acceptance and rejection of each of the demands put forward by the parties should be written. Because, if the court has forgotten to decide on one or more of these demands, it can make a complementary decision on these demands as per HMK 305/A after the verdict is given.

As it is known, HMK m. According to Article 353, 1, a, 6, "*the fact that a significant part of the party's request has not been decided*" is also a ground of appeal. It is also possible to appeal to the court of appeal to make a judgment about the claims that have not been decided by the court of first instance. However, in the case of appeal, the said deficiency can be eliminated by completing the more advantageous judgment, since it will send the file to the court of first instance for a decision on the request.¹¹

What is meant by requests that can be completed are "procedural requests." In other words, if a decision has not been made about the request despite the request, it is only possible

¹¹Akkaya, pages33.

to complete it. If a procedural claim, objection, or fact that will affect the result of the request is not observed while establishing the judgment, no application can be made to complete the judgment to remedy this deficiency. Because, if a complementary decision is made about such a defense, objection or claim regarding substantive law, one of the consequences of rendering the original decision ineffective or changing and correcting will emerge, which is not what the legislator intended with the completion of the provision. That is, since the procedural section in which the parties can put forward their claims and defenses within the scope of the principle of consolidation (Article 141 of the CPC) has been determined by law, the completion of the provision and its acceptance means a violation of the said principle. In other words, it is necessary to take legal action against a decision that is not given about a procedural request. As a matter of fact, if the party is right in the procedural objection because of the legal remedy review, the decision given will be overturned and it is necessary to take legal action regarding such non-procedural violation ¹².

A request that is forgotten to be decided on can be a primary or secondary request ¹³. For example, if the court has decided to reject the primary claim but has not given a decision on the secondary claim, the finalization of the judgment may be pursued in the adjourned case. However, as we mentioned above, to be able to go to completion, there should be no decision in the clause of the provision about the request that is completely or partially forgotten, and there should not be any statement regarding this request in the justification of the provision. In other words, if it is explained by the court in the reasoning part and the reasoning does not make a provision in the provision part as stated in the part, the completion cannot be requested. However, it is necessary to take legal action against the decision.

Likewise, if a decision is made without considering the claims and defenses of the parties, it is necessary to resort to legal action ¹⁴.

Moreover, to apply for the completion of the provision, the requests must be put forward in writing or verbally at the first trial.

¹²Derya Belgin Güneş, Completion of the Provision in Civil Procedure Law, İnÜHFD 12(1), p.319; Akkaya, pages39.

¹³Pekcanitez/Atalay/Özekes, Usul, p 435.

¹⁴ Akkaya, pages41.

To give an example of the significant differences that distinguish the completion of the provision from the correction and approval of the provision; Clear writing and calculation errors or matters exceeding the size of material errors cannot be corrected with the correction of the provision. At the same time, the contradiction between the reasoning part of the decision and the provision part cannot be resolved by affirmation¹⁵. Because the debts, which are given the rights granted to the parties in the provision clause, cannot be limited, expanded, or changed by way of correction or correction (HMK m.305, II). Although the regulation is regulated in the relevant article, as I have given detailed information in the proofreading part of our study, this article should also be applied by analogy for proofreading.

4.2.2. In terms of matters that need to be passed on judicially on their own

Another deficiency that can be demanded to complete the provision is, as the law puts it, "*issues that need to be adjudicated spontaneously*". The matters that should be included in the provision are regulated in Article 297 of the HMK. However, it is not necessary to go to completion for the deficiencies in each of the elements of the provision. In other words, a deficiency in a material error can be corrected by correction.

An example of matters that need to be passed on judicially on their own is the cost of litigation. As it is known, it is clearly regulated in Article 332 of the HMK that the court will decide *ex officio* on the cost of the trial. The provision to be made regarding the cost of litigation may be completely or partially forgotten by the court. In both cases, it is possible to apply for the completion of the judgment. In cases where the judge uses his discretion while making a spontaneous decision, the completion of the judgment cannot be applied. Namely, since the judge's right of discretion was used over his name and the decision was made as in the provision it is necessary to take legal action regarding this matter and to check whether the discretion of the judge is appropriate or not by the higher court. However, if the judge has a discretionary right but has **never decided about the cost of the trial, the** completion of the judgment may be requested.

In addition to the cost of litigation, it may be requested to complete whether the legal remedy is open and if the application period is missing. If the court has forgotten to decide

¹⁵Yilmaz, p.2989.

whether the legal remedy is open or not, there should not be a statement regarding this in both the reasoning of the judgment and the paragraph of the judgment to complete it ¹⁶. In other words, the absence of a related statement in the clause does not always necessitate the completion of the provision. If a determination regarding the legal remedy has been made in the justification part of the decision, but it has not been included in the provision clause, the defect here can also be corrected by correction.

4.3.Completion request

As explained above, upon the completion of the judgment, it is requested to make an additional decision on matters that are not included in the decision despite being requested in the first trial, or on matters that should be decided by the court on its own accord. The request for completion is made to the court that rendered the judgment, just like the correction and approval of the judgment, and it is examined by this court (art. 306). It is worth mentioning again that the party requesting the completion of the judgment cannot demand the issues that it did not demand in the first trial, in the petition for the completion of the verdict or during the trial. Regarding which parties, according to the view in the doctrine; Optional plaintiffs can request the completion of the judgment together with all their co-defendants, against the decision made regarding the case in which they are the main intervening party, or, if they are a secondary party, since they are not a party to the case, but only together with the person participating in the case ¹⁷.

Without the request of the parties, the court cannot proceed to the completion of the judgment ex officio. Because the text of the article is clear and there is no contradiction in this regard. (m.305/A). In other words, even if there is a deficiency in the matters that should be decided by the court on its own, the court cannot ex officio correct this deficiency and cannot make an additional decision without a request for completion. In terms of the court's inability to act without a request, the completion of the judgment is the same as the revision of the judgment and it is different from the correction.

¹⁶Derya Belgin Güneş, Completion of the Provision in Civil Procedure Law, İnÜHFD 12(1), p.321.

¹⁷ Akkaya, pages43, footnote sixty-six.

It is not important for the party to whom the request for completion is made, whether he asserts that he has requested the completion during the trial. There is no regulation on this issue in the text of the article. In that case, any party that has a legal interest in matters for which a full or partial decision has not been made, although it has not been brought forward at the trial stage, may request.

According to the accepted view in the doctrine, a legal benefit should not be sought for the request for the completion of the provision. Both parties have legal benefits in terms of making a positive or negative decision about the requests made to the court ¹⁸. Because, according to the wording of the law, "**each party**" can request me to complete it. The legislator has implicitly accepted that no legal benefit is sought. In general, a faster solution can be given as an example of the legal benefit of the parties in the request for the completion of the judgment, compared to the objection regarding the gaps in the decision or the parts where no provision has been made, in other words, the request for the completion of the judgment. For the reasons explained above, the legal benefit of the parties in the request for the completion of the judgment is indisputable.

The fact that a request for the completion of the provision has been made does not have any preventive effect on the application to the legal remedy against the original provision and its execution by force ¹⁹. This subject has been dealt with in more detail in the following pages of our study.

4.4.Duration

The request for the completion of the provision can be requested within one month from the notification of the final decision to the parties. The one-month period is a period of disqualification. According to German law, if the parties have been notified of the short decision and it is understood from this short decision that the judgment must be completed, the application period starts to run from this decision ²⁰. In practice in Turkish law, however, it cannot be determined in the short decision whether there is a deficiency listed in HMK art ²¹.

¹⁸ Akkaya, pages44.

¹⁹Tanriver, Civil Procedure Law, Volume I, Revised, Renewed and Enlarged 4th Edition, p.1043.

²⁰Transit citation Deya Belgin Güneş p,322, footnote sixty-three

²¹Belgin Güneş, p.322.

For this reason, the period starts to run from the notification of the reasoned decision to the party, not from the date on which the provision clause is annotated ²².

After the expiry of the one-month disqualification period, according to the accepted view in the doctrine, the party who missed the deadline may request completion by using the "reinstatement" procedure, if the conditions are met ²³.

If the appeal or the completion of the judgment is not applied in time and the judgment becomes final in this way, this provision does not constitute a final judgment in the second lawsuit filed against the forgotten (not decided) request. Because "a provision constitutes a final judgment only for those that have been adjudicated among the claims put forward in the lawsuit or in the counter lawsuit" (article 303/2) ²⁴. However, the most crucial point to be considered for filing an additional lawsuit here is whether the forgotten request is suitable to be the subject of an additional lawsuit. For example, litigation expenses are such that they cannot be subject to a separate lawsuit ²⁵.

5. procedure

The completion of the provision, how the request will be made and the procedural procedures after this request are regulated in Article 306 of the HMK. It is criticized in the doctrine that the procedure for the completion of the judgment is regulated together with the procedure for making the affirmation ²⁶.

The party who will demand the completion of the judgment must apply with a petition to the court that gave the judgment that it wants to be completed. A copy of the petition is served to the other party. ("FAQ - Family Law Attorney") The other party can respond to the request for completion with a sample petition as many as the number of parties, within an appropriate response time determined by the court. This reply is notified to the party requesting completion (M.306.1). The court has discretion in determining the response time. In addition, it is not possible to submit second petitions after the reply petition.

22 Akkaya, pages45.

23 Akkaya, pages45.

24 Baki Kuru, page 1587

25 Supreme Court IBK, dated 29.5.1957, 1957/4. E. 1957/16 K.

26 Pekcanitez/ Atalay/Özokes, Law No. 7251, p.280.

As a rule, the court decides on the completion request by examining the file. However, if the court deems it necessary, it may invite the two parties to make their oral explanations (art. 306, 2). In this framework, if complementary decisions have been requested on important points regarding the merits of the dispute, which have not been fully or partially decided despite being put forward in the trial, this request should be examined by holding a hearing. For example, if no or sufficient examination has been made by the court at the stage of the investigation regarding the request for which an additional decision is requested, a decision should be made by holding a hearing on the issue for which the additional decision is requested. However, if the request for completion is caused by deficiencies in matters that the court should decide on its own, such as the ²⁷required litigation expenses, attorney's fees, then a complementary decision must be made over the file without holding a hearing .

If it is decided to hold a hearing on the request for completion, if one or both parties do not attend the hearing, Article 150 of the CPC cannot be applied. That is, the regulation on the completion request procedure (article 306) refers to article 304. Article 304 states that “ *if the parties do not come upon the invitation, a decision can be made by examining the file.*” It has clearly excluded the application of Article 150 of the HMK in such cases by making a regulation.

If an additional decision is made regarding the completion request, the court acts according to the second paragraph of article 304. According to the article, the additional decision regarding the completed issues is written, signed, and sealed under the copies in the court and on a separate paper to be attached to them.

6. The Completion Request Does Not Prevent the Finalization of the Judgment and the Execution of the Judgment

As with the request for the correction of the judgment, the finalization of the judgment does not stop with the request for the completion of the judgment. Because, with the duly notification of the judgment to the parties, the application period for legal action begins to run, and if no legal remedy is applied at the end of the period, the judgment becomes final. Conversely, since the application periods for the legal remedy are processed separately by

²⁷Arslan, Yılmaz, Taşpınar Ayaz, Hanağası, Civil Procedure Law, Updated 7th Edition, Ankara-2021, p.724.

requesting the completion of the judgment, the finalization of the judgment cannot be prevented and postponed only by the request for completion without resorting to the legal remedy within the time limit.

Likewise, on the assumption that the judgment has been enforced, the execution of the judgment cannot be prevented by requesting the completion of the judgment. Because, in EBL articles 33 and 33/a, the execution of the judgment cannot be prevented or postponed with a request for completion, since it seeks that certain conditions and conditions have been fulfilled for the institution of postponement of execution to become functional, and since there is no regulation regarding the request for the completion of the judgment in the relevant provisions.

7. Decisions on Completion Request

Upon the request for the completion of the provision, the court decides to reject or accept the request. Upon the acceptance of the request, a "supplementary provision" is given ²⁸.

If the request for completion does not meet the necessary conditions, the court decides to reject the request. Both decisions are in the nature of "additional decision" in terms of legal definition. Separately, the decision is notified to the parties of the case.

The decision of acceptance or rejection given upon the request for completion shall be written under the original provision or on a separate paper to be attached to it (art.304, II). Since the supplementary decision is a part of the original decision (by analogy with Article 437/5), the base number of the supplementary decision must be the same as the base number of the original decision. This point shows its importance especially in terms of legal remedy. When legal remedies are applied against both the original judgment and the decision made upon the request for completion, the examination of both decisions will be made together in a timely manner by acting on the same basis number ²⁹.

However, if the case file has been sent to the court of appeal due to the appeal against the decision before the request for the completion, and if an appeal is made against the additional decision of the court upon the request for completion, these two appeal applications

²⁸Tanriver, Civil Procedure Law, Volume I, Revised, Renewed and Enlarged 4th Edition, p.724

²⁹Öztek/Taşpınar Ayvaz/Kale, "Some Explanations on the Law on the Amendment of the Code of Civil Procedure and Some Laws dated March 20, 2020, and Evaluation of the Bill" TBBD, 149, 2020, p.137.

are filed in different legal chambers, HMK m. There is no regulation in 305/A and m.306. To prevent this inconvenience, it would be appropriate to examine the articles 166/1 and 5 of the HMK by applying them by analogy and combining them in the same law office³⁰.

7.1. Legal nature of the supplementary provision (additional decision)

According to German and Austrian law, the supplementary provision is a provision independent of the main provision and is a partial provision against the original provision³¹.

According to the majority opinion in Turkish law, the supplementary provision is a partial provision³². However, although partial provision is accepted, it cannot be separated from the main provision since it is a decision that completes the original provision with the reference to article 304 of the CPC article 305/A. Because, according to an opinion in the doctrine, "the additional decision made upon the request for completion should be accepted as an integral part of the original provision."³³ In this case, although it complies with the definitions of the partial provision, both the legal definition of the complementary decision and the views in the doctrine cannot be the subject of the additional decision independent from the main provision.

The additional decision made upon the request for the completion of the judgment cannot be evaluated independently of the original decision. Because if the root decision is subject to enforcement, the additional decision should be submitted to the relevant enforcement office and a repayment order should be issued and the decision should be executed accordingly. If the root decision has been executed until the completion decision is made, this time, the issues that are not decided in the root decision can be executed by submitting an additional decision if there is no recurrence in the collection. During the execution phase, the debtor may object to repeated proceedings, violation of the judgment or repetition (redemption) in collection.

8. The Relationship Between the Act Against the Main Judgment and the Decision to Complement the Judgment

30 Baki Kuru, page 1589

31 Transit citation Deya Belgin Güneş p,324, footnote seventy-six.

32 Pekcanitez/Atalay/Özekes, Usul, p 436.

33 Arslan, Yılmaz, Taşpınar Ayaz, Hanağası, Civil Procedure Law, Updated 7th Edition, Ankara-2021, p.724.

The plaintiff, whose decision on one or more of the main and auxiliary requests in the petition has been forgotten (in the judgment), may apply to appeal in time to correct this mistake (m.353/a-6), or to complete the judgment within one month from the notification of the final decision. can apply. Applying for the completion of the provision against an incomplete provision does not prevent the application of legal remedies against the original provision. In the same way, it is possible to apply for the completion of the provision after the application of legal remedies against the original provision, and the party has the right to choose here.

Can the matters left incomplete in the judgment be made as grounds for appeal without the completion of the judgment?

Before the completion of the judgment was accepted in our law, if there was an issue left incomplete in the judgment, there would be no hesitation in making it a reason for appeal³⁴. In this case, it sends the file to the court of first instance, citing the fact that the court of appeal did not decide on an important part of the request (HMK art.353, I, a, 6). However, if the deficiency is not related to an important part, the court of appeal may also decide for the forgotten part (HMK m.353, III).

9. Remedies Against Supplementary Judgment

Against the decision of acceptance or rejection to be given by the court regarding the completion of the judgment, a legal remedy can be applied independently of the original decision (art. 305/A, Ic2). If a legal remedy is applied against the additional decision given for the completion of the provision, the legal remedy review within the scope of this application is made only about the completion decision. In other words, the review of the legal remedy against the additional decision is made only about the decision to complete the judgment and its judgment³⁵.

As you know, the court cannot take any decision on unclaimed matters under the name of supplementary provision; He cannot make any changes in the context of the matters in which he has declared his will in a positive or negative way in the pre-judgment conclusion part³⁶.

³⁴Law proposal on the amendment of the Code of Civil Procedure and some laws(2/2735) and the Report of the Justice Commission, p,17; Budak/Karaaslan, Law No. 7251, p.25; Budak/Karaaslan, Usul, p.307.

³⁵ Akkaya, pages54.

³⁶Tanriver, Civil Procedure Law, Volume I, Revised, Renewed and Enlarged 4th Edition, Ankara-2021

Therefore, the court of appeal will examine these issues against the completion decision and legal control of the completion decision will be made.

In addition, since the courts of appeal are not only supervising the decisions of the courts of first instance, but are also the courts of adjudication, the completion of the judgment can be applied not only for the first instance court completion decisions but also for the appellate court completion decisions³⁷. There is no restriction on this issue in the text of the article.

As stated above, the finalization of the judgment cannot be prevented or postponed with the request for the completion of the judgment. If the parties do not resort to legal action within the time limit, they are deemed to have given up on taking legal action.

The most important contradiction here arises when the original decision is not subject to legal action. According to the view in the doctrine, it is not considered important whether the actual decision is subject to legal remedy or not³⁸. However, if the main provision is not subject to legal remedy in terms of legal order, the additional decision should also be closed to legal remedy.

Another issue that needs to be discussed is whether the decision to be made by the Supreme Court upon the request for completion of the original decision in the legal remedy review is awaited. In other words, the waiting issue is whether it will be done or not.

As you know, in matters where there is no regulation in the appeal proceedings, there is a regulation that the valid trial procedure will be applied in the first instance court. In that case, in cases where the examination regarding the above possibility, that is, the request for completion, is not completed and no additional decision is made, the Court of Appeals HMK m. According to 165, the appeal against the original decision may make the proceedings a pending matter.

10. Application of Hmk 305/A Article in Terms of Time

The legislator has not foreseen any transitional provision in terms of the article of law regarding the completion of the provision. In that case, the principle of immediate application

37 Baki Kuru, page 1587

38 Akkaya, pages53.

of the civil procedure law rules, if they do not affect the completed works in accordance with the accepted general procedural rules in terms of time ³⁹(HMK art. 448) will be valid.

Since the law amendment regarding the completion of the provision entered into force on 28.7.2020, the issue that needs to be discussed is will Article 305/A of HMK be applied in cases filed before this date? In our opinion, in accordance with the above-mentioned law article and general procedural rules, regardless of the date of filing the lawsuit, this provision will be used in all decisions that have been made or will be made after 28.7.2020. However, according to an opinion in the doctrine, since the date of notification will cause inequality between these parties due to the possibility of notification to one of the parties before 28.7.2020 and to the other after 28.7.2020, it is necessary to act according to the final decision date of the court and to apply the institution of completion of the judgment ⁴⁰. If we accept that the decisions made before .2020 have been notified until today (it is almost impossible that they have not been notified), it is highly likely that the one-month application period has expired even if we do not, then it should be accepted that such a retrospective discussion is also fictitious. However, it should be noted that, in accordance with the principle of immediate implementation, in case of notification of a decision made before 28.7.2020 after 28.7.2020, an application can be made to this institution.

11. Similarities and Differences between the Completion of the Judgment and the Rectification and Attribution of the Judgment.

Although they are regulated in the same section in the HMK, the completion of the provision differs from the other institutions mentioned.

11.1. Differences between the correction and the provision

The purpose of the correction of the provision is to try to correct the material errors in the provision, as explained **above** . What is meant by material errors is simple spelling and calculation errors or other similar obvious errors in the provision. One of the most important rules in the correction of the provision is that the rights and debts granted to the parties cannot

³⁹Pekcanitez/Atalay/Özekes, Usul, p.17.

⁴⁰Akkaya, Completion of the judgment in the Civil Procedure Law, p.23.

be narrowed or expanded, and no additional decision is made regarding the requests for which the judgment is forgotten. In addition, the correction of the judgment can be made by the request of the parties or by the court ex officio.

As it can be understood, the main differences between the completion of the provision and the correction of the provision are out of question. First, the completion of the judgment is the remedy against the final decision, and the correction is only a legal remedy for the clause, as it can be understood from the text of the article. In addition, although the legislator does not set a time limit for the correction of the judgment, a 30-day period of disqualification has been determined for the completion of the judgment. The other most significant difference is that, as explained above, the aim of the completion of the judgment is the provision of additional decision for the requests that are forgotten to be decided or the issues that need to be decided ex officio. Another explanation is to eliminate gaps and deficiencies. In the revision of the provision, additional decisions cannot be made for matters that are forgotten or that need to be decided ex officio. Only the writing and calculation errors in the clause are tried to be corrected.

11.2. Differences between the adjudication of the provision

Again, as we explained in detail above, the purpose of the revision of the provision is to clarify the uncertainty (hesitancy) in the provision or to eliminate the contradictory results (contradictions) contained in the provision. The approval of the judgment is needed when more provisions are executed, and therefore, the prerequisite of requesting approval until the execution of the judgment is completed by the lawmaker. To reiterate, the institution of affirmation was introduced to ensure the execution of the Rule, that is, to eliminate the hesitations and contradictions in the provision.

Again, the rights granted to the parties and the obligations imposed on the parties cannot be limited, expanded, changed and a decision cannot be made regarding the forgotten requests. In other words, no decision can be made under the name of affirmation decision on a matter that has never been decided.

Completion of the judgment is against the final decision, as we mentioned when mentioning the differences with the correction, and it is not only related to the provision clause of the decision. Attribution and rectification are related to the provision clause of the decision.

In addition, another difference is that while the request for completion must be applied within 30 days, there is no such clear time limit for affirmation, and affirmation can be requested until the judgment is executed. The most significant difference is that, as explained above, the aim of the completion of the judgment is the court's additional decision for the forgotten requests or the issues that need to be decided ex officio. In other words, it is the elimination of gaps and deficiencies in the final decision. On the other hand, in the determination of the provision, additional decisions cannot be made for matters that are forgotten or that need to be decided ex officio.

11.3. Common features with Correction and Affirmation

The most important common feature of the completion of the provision and correction and correction is that these three institutions are not a legal remedy, but a legal remedy, as accepted in the doctrine.

One of the common features with declaration of facts is that the request for ordination and completion is requested only by the parties, and this institution cannot be made operational by the court ex officio. In addition, a joint arrangement has been made with the HMK article 306 regarding the method of correction and completion.

12. Conclusion

As explained above, in our law, there are institutions of correction for the correction of material errors and the explanation of unclear or contradictory statements after the court gives a verdict and withdraws from the file. With the HMK article 305/A, the institution of completing the provision has been added to eliminate the deficiencies in the provision.

The institution of completion of the provision has been in existence since 1 October 2011, when CPC No. 6100 entered into force.

We can define the completion of the provision as the making of an additional decision on matters that were not partially or completely decided, although it was brought forward by the parties during the trial process and the subject of a lawsuit should be taken into consideration by the court ex officio.

There is no clear regulation in the law regarding the legal nature of the institution of completion of the provision. However, the legal nature of the institution in question is narrow and technically not a legal remedy. Because the completion of the provision has neither the transmitting nor the suspensive effect, which are the typical characteristics of legal remedies in a narrow and technical sense. Completion of the provision is accepted as a legal remedy, such as the correction and the annulment of the provision.

Completion of the judgment was claimed by the parties in the trial, but the court did not express any will in the judgment, either positively or negatively, that is, although the forgotten demands or it should be decided spontaneously, the decision was made without going to the legal remedy on the issues that were not partially or completely decided. It aims to give additional decision by the court.

As we have explained in detail above, several conditions must be met at the same time to complete the provision. In other words, in order for the parties to make a request for completion, the existence of a final decision given by the court, the claims of the parties in the final decision in question or a matter that should be decided ex officio by the court should not have been decided, and a request for completion should be submitted to the court that made the decision within 30 days. .

With the completion of the judgment, it is requested to make an additional decision on matters that are not included in the decision although requested in the first trial, or on matters that need to be decided by the court itself. The request for completion is made to the court that rendered the judgment, just like the correction and approval of the judgment, and it is examined by this court.

Without the request of the parties, the court cannot proceed to the completion of the judgment ex officio. Because the text of the article is clear and there is no contradiction in this regard.

The request for the completion of the provision can be requested within one month from the notification of the final decision to the parties. The one-month period is a period of disqualification.

After the expiry of the one-month disqualification period, according to the accepted view in the doctrine, the party who missed the deadline may request completion by using the "reinstatement" procedure if the conditions are met.

If the appeal or the completion of the judgment is not applied in time and the judgment becomes final in this way, this provision does not constitute a final judgment in the second lawsuit filed against the forgotten (not decided) request. Because “a judgment constitutes a final judgment only for those that have been ruled out of the claims put forward in the case or in the counterclaim.

The party requesting the completion of the judgment must apply with a petition to the court that gave the judgment that it wants to be completed. A copy of the petition is served to the other party. (“FAQ - Family Law Attorney”) The other party can respond to the request for completion with a sample petition as many as the number of parties, within an appropriate response time determined by the court. This reply is notified to the party requesting completion (M.306.1). The court has discretion in determining the response time. As a rule, the court decides on the completion request by examining the file. However, if the court deems it necessary, it may invite the two parties to make their oral explanations.

If an additional decision is made regarding the completion request, the court acts according to the second paragraph of article 304. According to the article, the additional decision regarding the completed issues is written, signed, and sealed under the copies in the court and on a separate paper to be attached to them.

As with the request for the correction of the judgment, the finalization of the judgment does not stop with the request for the completion of the judgment.

Because, with the duly notification of the judgment to the parties, the application period for legal action begins to run, and if no legal remedy is applied at the end of the period, the judgment becomes final. Likewise, on the assumption that the judgment has been enforced, the execution of the judgment cannot be prevented by requesting the completion of the judgment.

Against the decision of acceptance or rejection to be given by the court regarding the completion of the judgment, a legal remedy can be applied independently of the original decision (art. 305/A, Ic2). If a legal remedy is applied against the additional decision given for the completion of the provision, the legal remedy review within the scope of this application is

made only about the completion decision. In other words, the review of the legal remedy against the additional decision is made only about the decision to complete the judgment and its judgment.

Just as in the correction and clarification of the judgment, a higher court may be appealed against the completion decision of the higher court in the completion of the judgment.

Since the law amendment regarding the completion of the provision entered into force on 28.7.2020, the issue that needs to be discussed is will Article 305/A of HMK be applied in cases filed before this date? In our opinion, in accordance with the above-mentioned law article and general procedural rules, regardless of the date of filing the lawsuit, this provision will be used in all decisions that have been made or will be made after 28.7.2020. However, according to an opinion in the doctrine, since the date of notification will cause inequality between these parties due to the possibility of notification to one of the parties before 28.7.2020 and to the other after 28.7.2020, it is necessary to act according to the final decision date of the court and to apply the institution of completion of the judgment[187]]Obviously, if we accept that the decisions made before 28.7.2020 have been communicated until today (it is almost impossible that they are not notified), it is highly likely that the one-month application period has expired even if we do not, then it should be accepted that such a discussion in the past is also fictitious. However, it should be noted that, in accordance with the principle of immediate implementation, in case of notification of a decision made before 28.7.2020 after 28.7.2020, an application can be made to this institution.

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